

Event metadata

Event title	AI in the life sciences: Exploring possibilities, inspiring change
Event type	Webinar series
Date of event	11 June - 17 September 2025
Topic description	<p>Join us for a series of webinars where we explore how Artificial Intelligence (AI) is shaping the future of life sciences!</p> <p>This series provides an accessible introduction to AI while giving direct access to experts and practical insights into real-world applications. Designed to inspire and help you recognise potential applications of AI in the life sciences, these webinars will spark new ways of thinking so that you can start applying AI in your work.</p> <p>The webinars include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A foundational session covering AI basics, its evolution, and why it matters for life sciences. Watch the recording here! • Guest speaker sessions where leading experts from academia and industry share how AI is being applied in different domains • Live Q&A to engage with speakers, ask questions, and participate in discussions
Speakers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dr Benjamin Goudey, Australian BioCommons • Dr Anna Trigos, PeterMac • Dr Maisie Li, CSIRO • Dr Túlio de Lima Campos, Oswaldo Cruz Foundation (Brazil) and University of Melbourne • Dr Vinícius W. Salazar, Melbourne Bioinformatics • Dr Carlos Santos-Martin, University of

	<p>Melbourne</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Dr Stefano Mangiola, University of Adelaide• Dr Anh TN Nguyen, Monash University• Dr Rebekah Harms, UNSW• Dr Yves Saint James Aquino, University of Wollongong• Tine Claeys, UGent• Dr Veit Schwämmle, SDU
Format description	A series of webinar presentations followed by a brief question and answer session
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/ai-series-2025
Licence	Materials are shared under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International agreement unless otherwise stated on the materials
Keywords	Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091 AI
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au
Audience	<p>Is this series for me?</p> <p>Are you:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Curious about AI but unsure how it applies to your work?• Working in life sciences and want to understand how AI is shaping the field?• Interested in learning from experts on domain specific AI applications?• Keen to explore ethical challenges in AI-driven research?• Looking for trusted resources to continue your AI learning journey? <p>If you answered yes to any of these questions, then this series is for you!</p>
Prerequisites	None
Technical requirements	None
Learning outcomes	

Training materials

Materials shared in this Zenodo record:

- Event metadata (PDF): Information about the event including, description, event URL, learning objectives, prerequisites, technical requirements etc.
- Campos (PDF): a PDF copy of the slides presented by Dr Túlio de Lima Campos during the webinar.
- Li (PDF): a PDF copy of the slides presented by Dr Maisie Li during the webinar.
- Salazar (PDF): a PDF copy of the slides presented by Dr Vinícius W. Salazar during the webinar.
- Harms (PDF): a PDF copy of the slides presented by Dr Rebekah Harms during the webinar.
- Veit (PDF): a PDF copy of the slides presented by Dr Veit Schwämmle during the webinar.

Materials shared elsewhere:

Deciphering AI for the Life Sciences - Dr Benjamin Goudey, Australian BioCommons

Recording:

 WEBINAR: Deciphering AI for the Life Sciences

Slides: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15110330>

Our journey incorporating AI into our cancer computational research - Dr Anna Trigos, PeterMac

Recording: AI in the life sciences - Dr Anna Trigos

Slides: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15770502>

Towards Human-AI Collaboration in Genomics and Bioinformatics - Dr Maisie Li, CSIRO

A Journey into Binary Classification Challenges in AI - Dr Túlio de Lima Campos, Oswaldo Cruz Foundation (Brazil) and University of Melbourne

Recording:

 AI in the life sciences - Dr Túlio de Lima Campos...

Deep Learning Meets the Deep Sea: AI in Microbial Oceanography - Dr Vinícius W. Salazar, Melbourne Bioinformatics

AI-Driven Discovery and Therapeutic Innovation in Fungal and Bacterial Pathogenesis - Dr Carlos Santos-Martin, University of Melbourne

Recording:

[▶ AI in the life sciences - Dr Vinícius W. Salazar an...](#)

Improving the interpretability of AI models for cell biology and precision medicine - Dr Stefano Mangiola, University of Adelaide

Bridging pharmacology and AI: Accelerating GPCR drug discovery with deep learning - Dr Anh TN Nguyen, Monash University

Recording:

[▶ AI in the life sciences - Dr Stefano Mangiola and ...](#)

Ensuring equity in the integration of artificial intelligence in engineering biology - Dr Rebekah Harms, UNSW

Data equity and the challenges of diversifying datasets for artificial intelligence - Dr Yves Saint James Aquino, University of Wollongong

Recording:

[▶ AI in the life sciences - Dr Rebekah Harms and D...](#)

AI-readiness of proteomics data: challenges, applications, and future perspectives - Tine Claeys, UGent

An overview of deep learning methods to enhance proteomics data analysis - Dr Veit Schwämmle, SDU

Recording:

[▶ AI in the life sciences - Dr Tine Claeys and Dr Ve...](#)